

Association of Maternal Body Mass Index with Materno-Fetal Outcome

Authors:

Dr. Shubhangi A. Mande¹, Dr. Jaga Jayadas², Dr. Pooja Mote³, Dr. Lakshmi Rachakonda⁴

¹Professor and HOU, Department of OBGY, MGM Medical College and Hospital, N-6 CIDCO, Aurangabad, 431003

²Senior Resident, Department of OBGY, MGM Medical College and Hospital, N-6 CIDCO, Aurangabad, 431003

³Assistant professor, Department of OBGY, MGM Medical College and Hospital, N-6 CIDCO, Aurangabad, 431003

⁴Professor and HOD, Department of OBGY, MGM Medical College and Hospital, N-6 CIDCO, Aurangabad, 431003

Corresponding Author:

Dr. Jaga Jayadas

Senior Resident, Department of OBGY, MGM Medical College and Hospital, N-6 CIDCO, Aurangabad, 431003

Article Received: 30-November-2023, Revised: 20-December-2023, Accepted: 10-January-2024

ABSTRACT:

Objective: To categorise pregnant women according to their BMI noted in first trimester and to note materno-fetal outcome in each group. Also to note the awareness of pre-pregnancy weight amongst pregnant women. **Method:** A cross sectional study conducted in the department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, MGM Medical College and Hospital, Aurangabad from December 2020 to December 2022. Pregnant women with singleton pregnancy having their first trimester height and weight record were included in this study. Total 322 participants that were admitted in the labour room during this period were stratified into 4 group based on obesity classification by WHO. The antenatal, intrapartum, postpartum and neonatal outcome was studied in each BMI category. Postpartum weight loss after 48 hours was also noted. **Result:** Majority of women did not know their pre conception weight in a developing country like India. Obesity is one of the factors for infertility and a significant women required the need for ART for conception. Abnormal weight gain was seen in abnormal BMI pregnant women and there was significant postpartum weight loss in overweight women. GDM, hypertensive disorder of pregnancy, FGR, failure of induction, mode of delivery are affected by the higher BMI of pregnant women. Macrosomia, lactation failure was also seen in obese women. **Conclusion:** Obesity in pregnant women is a serious concern as it can lead to complications during antenatal and perinatal periods, as well as long term effects on both the mother and the baby and close supervision and proper care can greatly improve the outcomes of pregnancy.

Keywords: *Body mass index, Maternal obesity, Macrosomia, Gestational diabetes mellitus*

INTRODUCTION:

Maternal obesity prevalence is increasing in many countries in the world, including Asia South-East Asian countries and is associated with a greater risk of mother and early neonatal deaths. Worldwide obesity has nearly tripled since 1975, with about 13% of adults being obese and about 39% of adults being overweight¹. Over the last 40 years, the global prevalence of obesity in women has increased 2.5-fold from 6% to 15%². Obesity is defined as pre-pregnancy BMI >30 and <35 kg/m²; morbid obesity is defined as pre-pregnancy BMI >or=35 kg/m². Well-controlled gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) is defined as mean blood glucose <105 mg/dl³. Maternal obesity increases the risk of a number of pregnancy complications, including preeclampsia, GDM, and cesarean delivery⁴. Excessive weight gain during pregnancy and postpartum retention of pregnancy weight gain are significant risk factors for later obesity in women⁵. The foetus is at risk of preterm birth, post-term pregnancy, macrosomia and increased neonatal intensive care unit admission. The increasing rate of

maternal obesity provides a major challenge to obstetric practice. Maternal obesity can result in negative outcome for both mother and foetus⁶. Maternal obesity increases the risk of a number of pregnancy complications and, as such, requires adjustment to routine prenatal care. Maternal obesity is a risk factor for spontaneous abortion (for both spontaneous conceptions and conceptions achieved through assisted reproductive technology), as well as for unexplained stillbirth (intrauterine fetal demise)⁷. The American College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists (ACOG) to recommend that at the prenatal visit, height and weight should be recorded for all women to allow calculation of body mass index and appropriate weight gain should be reviewed at the initial visit and periodically throughout pregnancy⁸. India is now facing a burden of under nutrition on one side, and the steadily increasing prevalence of overweight and obesity in affluent societies on the other side. Within Maharashtra, there are significant differences between rural and urban areas with rural areas being more affected by malnutrition and

Graph 2: Distribution of cases according to Age

Graph 2 shows that advanced maternal age is associated with obesity. (p value- 0.0014, significant)

Table 1(a): Incidence of preterm delivery in underweight women

Sr No	Gestational age	Normal (n=70) n (%)	Underweight (n=10) n (%)	p-value
1	Preterm	7 (2.17)	4 (1.24)	0.00997 (Significant)
2	Term	63 (19.56)	6 (1.8)	

Table 1(b): Incidence of preterm delivery in overweight women

Sr No	Gestational age	Normal (n=70) n (%)	Overweight (n=87) n (%)	p-value
1	Preterm	7 (2.17)	17 (5.2)	0.09
2	Term	63 (19.56)	70 (21.7)	

Table 1(c): Incidence of preterm delivery in obese women

Sr No	Gestational age	Normal (n=70) n (%)	Obese (n=90) n (%)	p-value
1	Preterm	7 (2.17)	20 (6.2)	0.04 (Significant)
2	Term	63 (19.56)	70 (21.7)	

Table 1: In my study it was observed that preterm delivery is significantly seen in underweight and obese women.

Table 2(a): Incidence of prolonged pregnancy in underweight women

Sr No	Gestational age	Underweight (n=8) n (%)	Normal (n=84) n (%)	p-value
1	Term	6 (1.8)	63 (19.56)	0.5
2	Prolonged Pregnancy	2 (0.6)	21 (6.5)	

Table 2(b): Incidence of prolonged pregnancy in overweight women

Sr No	Gestational age	Normal (n=84) n (%)	Overweight (n=95) n (%)	p-value
1	Term	63 (19.56)	70 (21.7)	0.8
2	Prolonged Pregnancy	21 (6.5)	25 (7.7)	

Table 2(c): Incidence of prolonged pregnancy in obese women

Sr No	Gestational age	Normal (n=84) n (%)	Obese (n=87) n (%)	p-value
1	Term	63 (19.56)	70 (21.7)	0.39
2	Prolonged Pregnancy	21 (6.5)	17 (5.2)	

Table 2 shows there was no correlation of prolonged pregnancy with BMI in my study.

Table 3(a): Distribution of cases according to conception in overweight women

Sr No	Conception	Normal (n=91) n (%)	Overweight (n=112) n (%)	p-value
1	Spontaneous	87 (27.01)	102 (31.6)	0.2
2	ART	4 (1.24)	10 (3.1)	

Table 3(b): Distribution of cases according to conception in obese women

Sr No	Conception	Normal (n=91) n (%)	Obese (n=107) n (%)	p-value
1	Spontaneous	87 (27.01)	91 (28.2)	0.014 (Significant)
2	ART	4 (1.24)	16 (4.96)	

Table 3 shows obesity is one of the factor for infertility and significant number of patient required the need for ART.

Graph 3: Distribution of women on awareness of preconception-weight

Graph 3 shows that majority (84%) were not aware about their preconception weight.

Table 4: Distribution of cases according to weight gain in pregnancy

Sr No	Weight gain in pregnancy (kg)	Underweight (n=12) n (%)	Normal (n=91) n (%)	Overweight (n=112) n (%)	Obese (n=107) n (%)	Total (n=322) n (%)
1	< 4	0	1 (0.31)	6 (1.8)	3 (0.9)	10 (3.1)
2	4 to 6	7 (2.1)	24 (7.4)	28 (8.6)	41 (12.7)	100 (31)
3	6 to 11	5 (1.5)	59 (18.3)	67 (20.8)	60 (18.6)	191 (59.3)
4	12 to 18	0	7 (2.1)	9 (2.7)	2 (0.6)	18 (5.59)
5	> 18	0	0	2 (0.6)	1 (0.31)	3 (0.9)

Table 4 shows abnormal weight gain is seen in abnormal BMI.

Table 5: Distribution of cases according to weight loss after 48 hours of delivery

Sr No	Weight loss after 48 hours of delivery (kg)	Underweight (n=12) n (%)	Normal (n=91) n (%)	Overweight (n=112) n (%)	Obese (n=107) n (%)	p-value
1	2 to 4	12 (3.7)	68 (21.1)	67 (20.8)	53 (16.4)	0.0006 (Significant)
2	5 to 7	0	23 (7.1)	43 (13.3)	49 (15.2)	
3	8 to 10	0	0	2 (0.6)	5 (1.55)	

Table 5 shows significant postpartum weight loss is seen in overweight patients.

Table 6: Distribution of cases according to BMI independent antenatal risk factors

Sr No	Antenatal complications	Underweight n (%)	Normal n (%)	Overweight n (%)	Obese n (%)	Total n (%)
1	Anaemia	6 (1.8)	39 (12.1)	54 (16.7)	36 (11.1)	135 (42)
2	Infectious disease	0	2 (0.6)	1 (0.3)	1 (0.3)	4 (1.24)
3	APH	0	4 (1.24)	1 (0.3)	3 (0.9)	8 (2.4)
4	Prolonged pregnancy	2 (0.6)	21 (6.5)	25 (7.7)	17 (5.2)	63 (19.5)
5	Heart disease	0	1 (0.3)	2 (0.6)	0	3 (0.9)
6	Liver disease	0	0	0	1 (0.3)	1 (0.3)
7	Rh negative Pregnancy	1 (0.3)	4 (1.24)	4 (1.24)	2 (0.6)	10 (3.1)
8	PROM	3 (0.9)	12 (3.7)	18 (5.6)	16 (4.9)	49 (15.2)
9	Previous LSCS	1 (0.3)	14 (4.3)	16 (4.9)	33 (10.2)	64 (19.8)
10	Seizure disorder	0	2 (0.6)	0	0	2 (0.6)

Table 6 shows distribution of incidence of various antenatal risk factors according to BMI classification.

Table 7: Antenatal risk factor affected by underweight BMI

Sr. no.	Antenatal Complications		Underweight (n=12) n (%)	Normal (n=91) n (%)	p-value
1.	Oligohydramnios	Yes	2 (1.94)	35 (33.9)	0.13
		No	10 (9.7)	56 (54.3)	
2.	FGR	Yes	10 (9.7)	42 (40.7)	0.015 (Significant)
		No	2 (1.94)	49 (47.5)	
3.	PROM	Yes	3 (2.9)	12 (11.6)	0.2
		No	9 (8.7)	79 (76.6)	

Table 7 shows that FGR significantly depends on maternal nutritional status.

Table 8: Antenatal risk factor affected by overweight BMI

Sr no.	Antenatal Complications		Normal (n=91) n (%)	Overweight (n=112) n (%)	p-value
1.	PIH	Yes	11 (5.4)	26 (12.8)	0.04 (Significant)
		No	80 (39.4)	86 (42.3)	
2.	GDM	Yes	6 (2.9)	18 (8.86)	0.03 (Significant)
		No	85 (41.8)	94 (46.3)	
3.	Thyroid Disorders	Yes	7 (3.4)	17 (8.37)	0.1
		No	84 (41.3)	95 (43.7)	
4.	Oligohydramnios	Yes	35 (17.2)	36 (17.7)	0.34
		No	56 (27.5)	76 (37.4)	
5.	Polyhydramnios	Yes	6 (2.9)	9 (4.4)	0.69
		No	85 (41.8)	103 (50.7)	
6.	FGR	Yes	42 (20.6)	36 (17.7)	0.04 (Significant)
		No	49 (24.13)	76 (37.4)	

Table 8 shows PIH, GDM and FGR is significantly associated with overweight BMI.

Table 9: Antenatal risk factor affected by obese BMI

Sr. no.	Antenatal Complications		Normal (n=91) n (%)	Obese (n=107) n (%)	p-value
1.	PIH	Yes	11 (5.5)	28 (14.14)	0.013 (Significant)
		No	80 (40.4)	79 (39.8)	
2.	GDM	Yes	6 (3.03)	24 (12.1)	0.0019 (Significant)

		No	85 (42.9)	83 (41.9)	
3.	Thyroid Disorders	Yes	7 (3.53)	12 (6.06)	0.4
		No	84 (42.4)	95 (47.9)	
4.	Oligohydramnios	Yes	35 (17.6)	34 (17.7)	0.32
		No	56 (28.8)	73 (36.8)	
5.	Polyhydramnios	Yes	6 (3.03)	8 (4.04)	0.8
		No	85 (42.9)	99 (50)	
6.	FGR	Yes	42 (21.2)	44 (22.2)	0.4
		No	49 (24.7)	63 (31.8)	

Table 9 shows PIH and GDM is significantly associated with obese BMI.

Table 10: Distribution of cases according to Mode of delivery

Sr No	Mode of delivery	Underweight (n=12) n (%)	Normal (n=91) n (%)	Overweight (n=112) n (%)	Class 1 Obesity (n=65) n (%)	Class 2 Obesity (n=33) n (%)	Class 3 Obesity (n=9) n (%)	Total (n=322) n (%)
1	Vaginal Delivery With Episiotomy	8 (2.4)	34 (10.5)	40 (12.4)	14 (4.3)	4 (1.2)	4 (1.2)	104 (32.2)
2	Vaginal Delivery Without Episiotomy	2 (0.6)	2 (0.6)	3 (0.9)	4 (1.2)	0	0	11 (3.4)
3	Vaginal Delivery With Tear	0	5 (1.55)	6 (1.8)	3 (0.9)	3 (0.9)	0	17 (5.2)
4	Instrumental Delivery	0	0	0	1 (0.3)	0	0	1 (0.3)
5	Elective LSCS	0	9 (2.7)	6 (1.8)	4 (1.2)	5 (1.55)	5 (1.55)	29 (9.0)
6	Emergency LSCS	2 (0.6)	41 (12.7)	57 (17.7)	39 (12.1)	21 (6.5)	0	160 (49.6)

Table 10 shows distribution of cases according to Mode of delivery. In majority of cases i.e. 160 emergency LSCS was performed.

Table 11(A): Comparison of mode of delivery in normal BMI and underweight women

Mode of Delivery	Normal (n=91) n (%)	Underweight (n=12) n (%)	p-value
Vaginal Delivery	41 (39.8)	10 (9.7)	0.012 (Significant)
LSCS	50 (48.5)	2 (1.94)	

Table 11(A) shows incidence of LSCS is significantly decreased in underweight women.

Table 11(B): Comparison of mode of delivery in normal BMI and overweight women

Mode of Delivery	Normal (n=91) n (%)	Overweight (n=112) n (%)	p-value
Vaginal Delivery	41 (20.1)	49 (24.1)	0.85
LSCS	50 (24.6)	63 (31.03)	

Table 11(B) shows in overweight patient the mode of delivery was comparable.

Table 11(C): Comparison of mode of delivery in normal BMI and obese women

Mode of Delivery	Normal (n=91) n (%)	Obese (n=107) n (%)	p-value
Vaginal Delivery	41 (20.7)	33 (16.6)	0.03 (Significant)
LSCS	50 (25.25)	74 (37.3)	

Table 11(C) shows obesity significantly affects mode of delivery.

Table 12: Distribution of cases according to intrapartum complication

Sr No	Intrapartum complication	Underweight n (%)	Normal n (%)	Overweight n (%)	Obese n (%)	Total n (%)
1	PPH	1 (0.3)	27 (8.3)	33 (10.2)	42 (13.04)	103 (31.9)
2	Shoulder dystocia	0	0	1 (0.3)	2 (0.6)	3 (0.9)
3	Inverted T incision in LSCS	0	2 (0.6)	1 (0.3)	1 (0.3)	4 (1.2)

Table 12 shows PPH is one of the common complication seen in abnormal BMI.

Table 13(A): Incidence of failed induction in normal BMI and overweight women

Failed Induction	Normal (n=29) n (%)	Overweight (n=43) n (%)	p-value
Yes	16 (26.3)	25 (34.7)	0.8
No	13 (18.0)	18 (25)	

Table 13(B): Incidence of failed induction in normal BMI and obese women

Failed Induction	Normal (n=29) n (%)	Obese (n=34) n (%)	p-value
Yes	16 (25.3)	27 (42.8)	0.03 (Significant)
No	13 (20.6)	07 (11.1)	

Table 13 shows failed induction of labour is associated with increasing BMI.

Table 14: Distribution of cases according to postnatal complication

Sr No	postnatal complication	Underweight n (%)	Normal n (%)	Overweight n (%)	Obese n (%)	Total n (%)
1	delayed ambulance	0	2 (0.6)	1 (0.3)	9 (2.7)	12 (3.7)
2	Thromboembolic event	0	0	1 (0.3)	0	1 (0.3)
3	prolonged catheter	0	12 (3.7)	13 (4.03)	18 (5.5)	43 (13.3)
4	febrile morbidity	1 (0.3)	6 (1.8)	4 (1.2)	2 (0.6)	13 (4.03)
5	UTI	1 (0.31)	2 (0.6)	0	0	3 (0.9)

6	Wound infection	1 (0.3)	6 (1.8)	7 (2.1)	10 (3.1)	24 (7.4)
7	ICU admission	0	7 (2.1)	4 (1.2)	6 (1.8)	17 (5.2)

Table 14 shows distribution of postnatal complication in various BMI. Incidence of thromboembolic event were less as all postoperative patients with BMI more than 30kg/m² and BMI >28kg/m² if associated with risk factors such as preeclampsia received LMWH (100%). Increased wound infection was seen with increasing BMI.

Table 15(A): Incidence of lactation failure in normal BMI and overweight women

Lactation failure	Normal (n=91) n (%)	Overweight (n=112) n (%)	p-value
Yes	6 (2.9)	13 (6.4)	0.22
No	85 (41.8)	99 (48.7)	

Table 15(B): Incidence of lactation failure in normal BMI and obese women

Lactation failure	Normal (n=91) n (%)	Obese (n=107) n (%)	p-value
Yes	6 (3.03)	28 (14.1)	0.00027 (Significant)
No	85 (42.9)	79 (24.5)	

Table 15 shows lactation failure significantly seen in obese women.

Table 16(A): Distribution of cases according to birth weight

Sr No	birth weight (kg)	Underweight (n=12) n (%)	Normal (n=91) n (%)	Overweight (n=112) n (%)	Obese (n=107) n (%)	Total (n=322) n (%)
3	< 2.5	7 (2.17)	36 (11.1)	37 (11.4)	36 (11.1)	116 (36)
4	2.5 to 4	5 (1.5)	55 (17)	74 (22.9)	65 (20.1)	199 (61.8)
5	> 4	0	0	1 (0.3)	6 (1.8)	7 (2.17)

Table 16(B): Distribution of cases according to birth weight

Birthweight (kg)	Normal (n=91) n (%)	Overweight (n=112) n (%)	p-value
2.5-4kg	74 (36.4)	65 (32)	0.04 (Significant)
>4kg	1 (0.3)	6 (1.8)	

Table 16 shows developing macrosomia is significantly associated with obese women.

DISCUSSION:

Obstetrician are in a key position to prevent and treat this obesity epidemic with adverse consequences to the mother and baby, therefore it is important to know the risk associated to address this issue with patients, supervise and give proper care to them.

This study was conducted in tertiary care centre during December 2020 to December 2022. We included 322

singleton pregnancies and were classified into four groups according to their BMI. Out of 322 women, majority were from overweight and obese category i.e.35% and 33% respectively followed by 28% normal BMI and 4% underweight. According to fifth and latest national family health survey NFHS-5 (2019-2021), the percentage of obese women was 24%. The

incidence rate of obese is likely to be higher in my study because it is a tertiary care centre.¹⁴

We observed that increase in maternal age and women belonging to urban areas are associated with increase in BMI. Anjana Verma et al. reported elderly age and higher education belonged to overweight and obese group in 2012.¹¹

In our study preterm delivery was associated with underweight ($p=0.009$) and obese women ($p=0.04$). In a study conducted by Bodnar in 2005, he demonstrated increased risk of spontaneous and idiopathic preterm births in obese women.¹⁵ Hendler had reported that maternal BMI ≥ 30 Kg/m² had less chances of spontaneous preterm delivery.¹⁶

There was no correlation of BMI with prolonged pregnancy in my study. Denison FC et al. reported median BMI noted in first trimester was higher in postdates compared to patients delivering at term.¹⁷ Obesity is associated with activation of HPO axis, increased clearance of cortisol likely to reduce placental corticotrophin releasing hormone production and consequently delivery timing being effected.

Obesity is one of the factors causing infertility and a significant number of obese women ($p=0.014$) require the need for assisted reproductive technique for conception. Amala Sunder et al. conducted a study in 2972 patients in which 3.7% incidence of IVF conception was reported with p value = 0.009 between BMI groups.¹⁸

In our study only 16% of women knew their pre conception weight while majority of them that is 84% were unaware of their pre conception weight. There is a need for counselling the women to note their pre conception weight. The system for classifying all pregnant women based on body mass index in normal day- to-day practice is yet to be adopted to prevent associated risk factors.¹⁹

Our study demonstrates that abnormal weight gain is seen in abnormal BMI. Mary Annfaucher et al. reported 47-72% obese women gained excess weight than recommended, being additional risk factor.²⁰

There was significant postpartum weight loss in overweight patients was seen in my study. Bodnar reported his study conducted in 2005 had increased weight loss in class 1 and 2 obese women.¹⁵

The following were seen to be independent of BMI in our study, Anaemia in my study population was not found significant in obese women. Elmaraigneret et al. reported obesity as a risk factor for iron deficiency anaemia and nutritional anaemia due to extensive release of cytokines from inflamed adipose tissue altering iron haemostasis.²¹

Risk of GDM was observed with women with overweight BMI ($p=0.03$) and obese BMI ($p=0.0019$) similar to other studies. Kalk P. et al conducted a study included 2049 mothers in Charite University Hospital reported increased BMI was associated with increased complications like GDM, Hypertension, pedal oedema and foetal macrosomia.²² Maternal obesity is

associated with hyperinsulinemia and hyperlipidemia. This enhances oxidative stress with decreased prostacyclin and increased peroxide production which results in vasoconstriction and platelet aggregation leading to increased risk of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. With a p value of 0.04 for overweight BMI women and 0.013 for obese women an increase in PIH, this study estimated a significant increase in PIH similar to other studies. Prabha et al. reported that linear relationship between increasing BMI and risk of developing preeclampsia and gestational Diabetes mellitus in a case control study conducted in 6020 pregnant women in 2014.¹²

In our study APH was independent of BMI which is contrary to study by Mamula et al. where increase in risk of antepartum haemorrhage was noticed in obese women which has been attributed to placental abruption.²³ A study conducted by Cedergren et al in 2004 did not find any increased risk for placental abruption in a study which had larger numbers of morbidly obese women, similar to the findings in our study.²⁴

There was increased risk of FGR with overweight category ($p= 0.04$); a trend also noticed in other studies. Also FGR is seen in underweight category ($p=0.015$). Power et al. in 2019 reported 10.4% of small for gestational age (SGA) births were due to underweight women who gained weight below recommendations.²⁵

In our study majority if cases underwent emergency LSCS in the normal and overweight category while the incidence of LSCS decreased significantly in underweight women. Obesity affects the mode of delivery. Obesity was a significant risk factor for both elective and emergency LSCS which was also seen in study conducted by Fyfe et al. They also reported significant risk of prelabour LSCS ($p = 0.02$) as well as increased rates of caesarean delivery in first stage (OR: 2.89) among obese. They reported similar rates of second stage LSCS among both obese and non-obese.²⁶ Rode et al. had demonstrated a fivefold increase in odds of instrumental deliveries among obese women. In our study there was only one patient who needed instrumental delivery.²⁷

PPH is one of the common complication seen in abnormal BMI. Sebire et al. reported increase in postpartum haemorrhage with higher BMI by 70%.²⁸ In our study increase in wound infection was seen in obese women ($p=0.0002$). Stamilio DM et al. conducted a cohort study in 585 women in 2014 which reported two-to-four-fold rise in wound infection, endometritis and wound hematoma in obese women.²⁹ While the incidence of thromboembolic event was less in all postoperative patients with BMI >30 kg/m² or 28kg/m² with comorbidities received LMWH as per institutional protocol.

Lactation failure is seen significantly in obese women ($p=0.0002$). Lisa H Amir et al. conducted a systematic review of obesity and breastfeeding intention,

initiation and duration in 2007 and it was noted delayed lactogenesis in obese women and are less likely to initiate breastfeeding than normal weight women.³⁰

In our study there was a significant association between macrosomia and obesity (p=0.04). In spite of the higher rates of macrosomia, there was no significant increase in shoulder dystocia in most of the obese mothers. Sahu et al had reported significantly higher rates of macrosomia among morbidly obese women (p = 0.02).³¹ Sheiner et al. felt that after having adjusted for diabetes mellitus, no significant association was found between macrosomia and obesity alone.³² Besides, Catalano had already demonstrated that GDM can be a confounding factor in a study between macrosomia and obesity.³³

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, obesity in pregnant women is a serious concern as it can lead to numerous complications during prenatal and antenatal periods, as well as long-term effects on both the mother and the baby. It is crucial for pregnant women who are obese to work closely with their healthcare provider to manage their weight and minimize the associated risks. Close supervision and proper care can greatly improve the outcomes of pregnancy for both the mother and the baby.

REFERENCES:

1. Haque R, Keramat SA, Rahman SM, Mustafa MUR, Alam K. Association of maternal obesity with fetal and neonatal death: Evidence from South and South-East Asian countries. *PLoS One*. 2021 Sep 2; 16(9): e0256725. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0256725. PMID: 34473759; PMCID: PMC8412251.
2. Jaacks LM, Vandevijvere S, Pan A, et al. The obesity transition: stages of the global epidemic. *Lancet Diabetes Endocrinol*. 2019; 7(3): 231- 240.
3. Yogev Y, Langer O. Pregnancy outcome in obese and morbidly obese gestational diabetic women. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol*. 2008 Mar; 137(1):21-6. Doi: 10.1016/j.ejogrb.2007.03.022. PMID: 17517462.
4. Lynch CM, Sexton DJ, Hession M, Morrison JJ. Obesity and mode of delivery in primigravid and multigravid women. *Am J Perinatol*. 2018; 25:163–167.
5. Rooney B, Schauburger C. Excess pregnancy weight gain and long-term obesity: one decade later. *Obstet Gynecol*. 2020; 100:245–252.
6. NJ Sebire, et al. Maternal obesity and pregnancy outcome: a study of 287213 pregnancies in London. *International journal of obesity* 2001
7. Leddy MA, Power ML, Schulkin J. The impact of

- maternal obesity on maternal and fetal health. *Rev Obstet Gynecol*. 2008 Fall; 1(4):170-8. PMID: 19173021; PMCID: PMC2621047.
8. ACOG Committee opinion no. 549: obesity in pregnancy. *American College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologist*. *Obstet Gynecol*. 2013 Jan.
9. Maharashtra CDC review, Overview of malnutrition situation in Maharashtra.
10. National academies press 1990 .5, Total amount and pattern of weight gain: physiological and maternal Determinants, 1990
11. Anjana Verma, et al. Maternal Body mass index and pregnancy outcome, *Journal of clinical and Diagnostic Research* 2012 November
12. Prabha Kumari, et al. Association between high maternal body mass index and Feto- maternal outcome, *Journal of obesity and metabolic research*.
13. Omkara Murthy K, et al. A study of body mass index in pregnancy and its correlation with maternal and perinatal outcome. *Indian Journal of obstetrics and gynaecology research* 2017
14. National Family Health Survey - 5 2019-21 http://rchiips.org/nfhs/factsheet_NFHS-5.shtml; http://rchiips.org/nfhs/NFHS-5_FCTS/India.pdf
15. Bodnar IM, Ness RB. The risk of preeclampsia rises with increasing prepregnancy BMI. *Ann epidemiol* 2005; 15(7) 475 -482
16. Hendler, Israel et al. “The Preterm Prediction Study: association between maternal body mass index and spontaneous and indicated preterm birth.” *American journal of obstetrics and gynecology* vol.192,3 (2005): 882-6. doi: 10.1016/j.ajog.2004.09.021
17. Denison FC, Price J, Graham C, Wild S, Liston WA. Maternal obesity, length of gestation, risk of postdates pregnancy and spontaneous onset of labour at term. *BJOG* 2008; 115:720–5.
18. Sundar, Amala et al. “Maternal Obesity: An Obstetric Risk.” *Cureus* vol. 14,9 e29345. 19 Sep. 2022, doi:10.7759/cureus.29345
19. A Gormican. Et al. Relationship Maternal weight gain, prepregnancy weight and infant birth weight. Interaction of weight factors in pregnancy.
20. Mary ann faucher, mary k barger, a systematic review on GWG in obese women by class of obesity and maternal neonatal outcome. *Women and birth* 28 (2015) e70- e79 {<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.wombi.2015.03.006>
21. Elmar Aigner, Alexandra Feldman and Christian datsz, study on obesity as emerging risk factor for iron deficiency nutritional anemia. *Nutrients* 2014. Sep; 6(9): 3587-3600 2
22. Kalk p et al. *European journal of medical research*

- 2009; 14 (5): 216 – 222. Impact of maternal BMI on neonatal outcome.
23. Mamula et al. The complications during pregnancy, labour and puerperium in women with an increased BMI at pregnancy term. *Cent. Eur. J. Med.* 2009; 4(1): 71-75
 24. Cedergren, Marie I. “Maternal morbid obesity and the risk of adverse pregnancy outcome.” *Obstetrics and gynecology* vol. 103,2 (2004): 219-24. doi:10.1097/01.AOG.0000107291.46159.00
 25. Power ML, Lott ML, MacKeen AD, Dibari JN, Schulkin J. Associations Between Maternal Body Mass Index, Gestational Weight Gain, Maternal Complications, and Birth Outcome in Singleton, Term Births in a Largely Non-Hispanic White, Rural Population. *J women’s Heal [Internet]*. 2019 Nov 1 [cited 2021 Dec 28];28(11):1563–8. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31038373/>
 26. Fyfe, Elaine M et al. “Risk of first-stage and second-stage caesarean delivery by maternal body mass index among nulliparous women in labor at term,” *Obstetrics and gynecology* vol. 117,6 (2011): 1315-1322. doi:10.1097/AOG.0b013e318217922a
 27. Rode, L., Kjærgaard, H., Ottesen, B. et al. Association Between Gestational Weight Gain According to Body Mass Index and Postpartum Weight in a Large Cohort of Danish Women. *Matern Child Health J* 16, 406–413 (2012). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10995-011-0775-z>
 28. Sebire NJ, Jolly M et al. “Maternal obesity and pregnancy outcome: a study of 287,213 pregnancies in London. *Int J of Obesity* 2001, 25:1175-1182.
 29. Stamilio DM et al. *Obstet gynecol.* 2014 aug; 124(2 pt 1): 227- 232.
 30. Amir, L.H et al. A systematic review of maternal obesity and breastfeeding intention, initiation and duration. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth* 7,9 (2007). <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2393-7-9>.
 31. Sahu, M.T., Agarwal, A., Das, V. and Pandey, A. (2007), Impact of maternal body mass index on obstetric outcome. *Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology Research*, 33: 655-659. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1447-0756.2007.00646.x>
 32. Sheiner, E., Levy, A., Menes, T.S., Silverberg, D., Katz, M. and Mazor, M. (2004), Maternal obesity as an independent risk factor for caesarean delivery. *Paediatric and Perinatal Epidemiology*, 18:196-201.
 33. Ehrenberg H, Mercer B, Catalano P. The influence of obesity and diabetes on the prevalence of macrosomia. *Am J Obstet Gynecol.* 2014;191: 964-968